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HARASSMENT AS A FORM OF VIOLENCE. LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST CLAIMS IN UKRAINE

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More than four million Ukrainians are victims of sexual harassment every year. Most victims of harassment do not seek psychological or legal assistance and are not held accountable.

Harassment (oppression, pretending) is a form of discrimination that includes any unwanted and irritating physical and verbal behavior that offends or humiliates a person or disrupts his or her privacy. In other words, harassment (persecution) consists of repeated and persistent actions against a person in order to torture, devalue and undermine his authority in the eyes of others, upset or provoke a reaction.

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Harassment is a collective term for gestures, statements, jokes and other actions that offend, humiliate or intimidate a person. Harassment is not always sexual. For example, when a person is accompanied by insult or whistling because of his orientation or race. You can fall victim to this discriminatory behavior anywhere: on the street, at school, at university, at work or on public transport.

The term "harassment" gained popularity in the United States in the 70's of the twentieth century - during the mass influx of women into their careers. Despite the fact that both men and women suffer from harassment, the percentage of victims of women is twice as high.

It is common in society to treat women primarily as sexual objects. When we look at a woman, by default we first evaluate what she looks like. This attitude works even when it comes to a high-ranking woman with a good career: is the figure of the new Minister of Justice attractive? It seems that in such situations it makes no sense. These women are not paid for their appearance, but for their knowledge and skills, but society still pays attention to the body and appearance.

Harassment can occur not only at work, but also in other areas in schools or on a regular walk. It can affect people of all ages and statuses. The consequences

can be both mental and physical. Unwanted touches, gestures, actions, jokes and hints related to appearance, unfortunately, are familiar to many women. All these are different manifestations of harassment. The main criterion is reciprocity: flirting is pleasing to both, and harassment is the "breaking" of the victim's personal boundaries without her consent. However, the limit here is very thin: a woman's fear or inability to say a clear "no" can be perceived by a man as approval of his actions.

The term "harassment" is absent in Ukrainian law, but some forms of harassment are indicated. Proving that you have been a victim of harassment is not easy, even though the perpetrator violates the Law on Ensuring Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men. In cases of sexual abuse, a person faces criminal liability.

In accordance with paragraph 6 of Art. 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men", sexual harassment is an act of a sexual nature, expressed orally (threats, intimidation, obscenities) or physically (touching, slapping), humiliation or insults to persons, material or otherwise subordination. Ukrainian law does not provide for liability for sexual claims.

However, there is Article 154 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine - "Coercion to sexual intercourse." According to Part 1, forcing a person to commit an act of a sexual nature with another person without his or her voluntary consent is punishable by a fine of up to 50,000 hryvnia or arrest for up to six months. According to Part 2, forcing a person without his or her voluntary consent to commit a sexual act with a person from whom the victim is material or dependent is punishable by a fine of up to one thousand non-taxable minimum incomes, citizens or restriction of liberty for up to two years.

Pursuant to part 3, the actions provided for in parts one or two of this article are related to the threat of destruction, damage or seizure of property of the victim or his close relatives or the threat of disclosure of information that discredits him or close relatives are punishable by up to three years in prison or imprisonment for the same term.

The second definition in the legislation, according to which forms of harassment can be classified, is gender-based violence: According to paragraph 7 of Art. 1 of this Law, gender-based violence - actions against persons because of their gender, or common customs or traditions in society (stereotypes about social functions (positions, responsibilities, etc.) of women and men), or related actions. preferably persons of a certain sex or disproportionately injured, causing physical, sexual, psychological or economic harm or suffering, including threats to do so, in public or private life.

Such a crime is subject to administrative liability under Article 173-2 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses. The sanction of the article provides for liability in the form of a fine of ten to twenty non-taxable minimum incomes or community service for a period of thirty to forty hours or administrative arrest for up to seven days.

In order to protect your rights and bring the violator to justice, first of all, you need to gather evidence: eyewitness testimony, other people who have been persecuted by this person, SMS messages, screenshots, emails, photos or videos that record discriminatory actions.

It is equally important to develop tactics of behavior with harasser. If you have unpleasant human behavior - constant touching, obsessive attention or persistent offers to drink coffee - you should voice it. Open conflict is always difficult, but in this case you are simply defining your boundaries. The person may not have felt that they are doing something unpleasant to you - and an explanation will help them realize their mistake and be more careful.

It is necessary to stock up on the support of loved ones: the purpose of harassment is often not in future sex or an attempt to spin a romance, but in the process of bullying.

One of the most important steps in combating harassment is to seek the help of professional lawyers. The lawyer will help to make a clear plan of action, how to act in a specific situation, where to focus and monitor the actions of law enforcement. If it is not possible to pay for the services of a private lawyer, you can use the free legal aid provided by the state.

Call the police by phone or contact the police department in person. If the police do not enter the case in the Unified Register of Pre-trial Investigations, ignore evidence and testimonies, do not interrogate the participants of the case, you can apply to the National Police Chief, apply to the Prosecutor's Office or the Verkhovna Rada Commissioner. The complaint, which will set out all the circumstances of the case on your behalf, must be considered within 15 days and an internal investigation launched.

Write a complaint to the HR manager, head of the company, company, educational institution, where to place all the circumstances and evidence. Contact the Ombudsman Hotline. If a person has applied to all instances, but there is no positive result, you can apply to the UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women.

Only the victim can report harassment, sexual assault or rape. So even if she told the incident to one of her relatives or friends, they could not report it to the police. The hardest thing in a harassment situation is to believe in your feelings

and not dismiss them as insignificant (in our culture, obsession is still considered a compliment). If you feel that your personal boundaries are being systematically violated, it is a matter of persecution.

You need to understand two things: the aggressor is not omnipotent, and you are not to blame for what is happening. The length of the skirt, your appearance, behavior and other factors are not excuses for harassment - as in other forms of violence, the blame lies solely with the aggressor. Therefore, it is not necessary to tolerate harassment and justify the harasser

References:

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3. Law of Ukraine “On principles of prevention and counteraction of discrimination in Ukraine” of September 6, 2012 No. 5207-VI.
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5. Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses (1984, December 7).

